
**A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF LITERARY MOVEMENTS IN 20TH
CENTURY EUROPE**

Zokirova Zaynab,

Chirchik State Pedagogical University

Tourism faculty Foreign language and literature:English.

Scientific supervisor: Xamitov Eldor,

English teacher, Chirchik State Pedagogical University.

Abstract: Invites an exploration of how different literary movements across Europe influenced, intersected, and differed from each other during the 20th century. This period was marked by significant social, political, and cultural changes, which deeply shaped the literature and art of the time.

Keywords: Modernism, surrealism, existentialism, absurdism, philosophical, social realism, postmodernism, poverty.

Modernism was a broad movement focused on breaking away from traditional forms and experimenting with new styles and techniques. Writers wanted to capture the confusion and loneliness people felt in the modern world. They used techniques like stream-of-consciousness (writing as thoughts come to mind) and fragmented stories to show complex inner experiences.

Key Figures: Writers like James Joyce (*Ulysses*), Virginia Woolf (*To the Lighthouse*), and Franz Kafka (*The Trial*) were central to Modernism.

Comparison: Modernism grew in response to the rapid changes and hardships of the early 20th century, including World War I. It moved away from the more straightforward depictions of life in 19th-century literature and portrayed a deeper sense of psychological struggle.

Surrealism (1920s-1930s)

Overview: Surrealism started in France and emphasized the imagination, the unconscious mind, and dreams. Influenced by Freud's ideas on psychoanalysis,

Surrealists believed that creativity came from tapping into the subconscious. Their works often involved strange, dreamlike scenes and automatic writing (writing without thinking too much).

Key Figures: André Breton, who wrote the Manifesto of Surrealism, and poets like Federico García Lorca and Paul Éluard were important to the movement.

Comparison: While Modernism aimed to portray reality in new ways, Surrealism often ignored reality completely, exploring the irrational and the bizarre. They intersected in their interest in the mind, but Modernism was more serious and analytical, while Surrealism embraced chaos and dreams.

Existentialism and Absurdism (1940s-1950s)

Overview: Existentialism and Absurdism explored themes of isolation, freedom, and the search for meaning in a universe that seemed indifferent or absurd. These writers questioned traditional beliefs and portrayed characters dealing with life's uncertainties and lack of meaning.

Key Figures: Major writers included Jean-Paul Sartre (Nausea), Albert Camus (The Stranger), and Samuel Beckett (Waiting for Godot).

Comparison: Existentialism and Absurdism shared some themes with Modernism, especially the sense of alienation. However, they were more directly philosophical, focusing specifically on questions about life's meaning, often in plain and simple language.

Social Realism (1930s-1950s)

Overview: Social Realism aimed to represent the lives of everyday working people, often highlighting social issues, poverty, and oppression. Many writers of this movement used their work to expose injustice and reflect on the hardships of ordinary life.

Key Figures: Bertolt Brecht (known for his plays), George Orwell (1984), and Ignazio Silone (Fontamara) were key writers.

Comparison: Unlike Modernism or Existentialism, Social Realism used straightforward language to reach a broad audience, focusing less on personal inner

struggle and more on exposing social problems. It was more politically engaged than other movements, often aiming to inspire change.

Postmodernism (1960s-1980s)

Overview: Postmodernism is characterized by irony, humor, and mixing different styles. It questions whether there is any one "truth" and often plays with narrative techniques, blending fact and fiction and frequently breaking the "fourth wall" (directly acknowledging the reader).

Key Figures: Writers like Italo Calvino (*If on a Winter's Night a Traveler*), Umberto Eco (*The Name of the Rose*), and Vladimir Nabokov (*Pale Fire*) are known for their postmodern work. Magic Realism (1970s-1990s)

Characteristics: While more commonly associated with Latin American writers, Magic Realism also influenced European literature. This movement combines realistic narrative with magical elements, often rooted in folklore, mythology, or supernatural elements integrated into everyday life, questioning the boundaries between reality and fantasy.

Key Figures: Milan Kundera (*The Unbearable Lightness of Being*), Günter Grass (*The Tin Drum*).

Comparison: While Postmodernism and Magic Realism share an interest in blending reality with the absurd or fantastical, Magic Realism emphasizes a more organic integration of magical elements, focusing less on irony and more on narrative flow and cultural identity.

Comparative Analysis

Political Influence: 20th-century European literature often reflects the intense political climates of the time. Surrealism and Existentialism emerged in response to political disillusionment; Social Realism was tied to political and social critique; and Postmodernism developed in a world where confidence in "grand narratives" had eroded.

Philosophical Depth: Existentialism and Absurdism share a focus on the search for meaning in life, while Modernism sought new ways to express individual

consciousness. Surrealism and Magic Realism are less explicitly philosophical but invite readers to expand their perception of reality.

Narrative Techniques: Modernism and Postmodernism significantly reshaped narrative structures through fragmentation, self-reflexivity, and irony. Social Realism, however, maintained a more traditional narrative style, aiming to be accessible to a broad audience. Surrealism's narrative style is less conventional, often mimicking dream logic.

Conclusion

Studying 20th-century European literary movements as part of a comparative analysis highlights how literature was a mirror for both individual and collective experiences, capturing the complexities of modern and postmodern life. Each movement contributed unique perspectives, narrative techniques, and thematic concerns, collectively expanding the scope of European literature.

Reference

1. *"The Cambridge Companion to Modernism"* by Michael Levenson
2. *"A History of Literary Criticism: From Plato to the Present"* by M.A.R. Habib
3. *"The Oxford Handbook of Modern European Literature"*
4. "Modernism: A Guide to European Literature 1890-1930" by Peter Brooker
5. "A Companion to Postmodernism" edited by Stuart Sim
6. "The Routledge Companion to Surrealism" edited by Michael Richardson and Anna Balakian
7. "The Cambridge Companion to Existentialism" edited by Steven Crowell
8. "Magic Realism: A Global Perspective" by Lois Parkinson Zamora
9. "The Art of the Novel" by Milan Kundera
10. Internet Encyclopedia of Philosophy